

Zinc and Silver Migration During Rechargeable Silver-Zinc Cell Cycling

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ABSTRACT

A study has been established at NAVSURFWARCENDIV Crane to obtain zinc and silver migration rate data on cellulosic separators derived from a variety of cellulose and cellophane sources, in silver-zinc alkaline rechargeable cells. These data are to be related to cycle and wet life data from the model electrochemical cells as a function of separator composition for the rechargeable cell set. The first examples used in this program are cells of 28 Ahr capacity, identical in every respect except for the separator composition, which are being tested in statistically significant numbers under identical temperature and relative humidity conditions, with 45% KOH as the electrolyte. The cycle life test regime is C/5 discharge to 1.30 V and C/30 and C/60 charge to 2.03 V continuous cycling, while the wet life test regime includes a 30-day wet stand at full charge between cycles. At the outset of the cell testing, a baseline cell was selected from each set in the matrix after the formation cycling was complete, and the silver and zinc migration through successive separator layers were determined. Also, at intervals during life cycle and wet life, and as cells fail the life tests, the measurements will be repeated. In this way a correlation may be established between silver and zinc migration rates under charge-discharge conditions in actual cells and the cycle and wet life of the respective cell types. Eight separator compositions, all cellulose-based, are being evaluated.

The purpose of the study is to utilize the cycle and wet life data which are, in part, a function of the formation of soft and hard shorting in the rechargeable cell set, to designate a "best" separator for incorporation into actual production cells by the manufacturing community for silver-zinc rechargeable cells. The recommendations will take the form of minimum separator physical properties which are beneficial to cell performance and long life, resulting in an improvement in the assets available for Navy Fleet use.

This paper will discuss the data available to date on silver and zinc migration and their relationship to cell cycling at several stages during the cell life.

History

About 60 years ago, the utility of regenerated cellulose film as a battery separator was recognized as a forward step which advanced the silver-zinc battery to a practical system. The French professor Henri Andre, who had been working with the silver-zinc system since the late 1920's, published a paper (1) in 1941 in which he stated "...that the short life of the system could be considerably improved by the introduction of a suitable semipermeable separator." In this way the migration of silver colloid to the negative plate was prevented, as well as the short circuits due to zinc "trees" from the negative to the positive plate. Not until the introduction of such membranes could the great energy content per unit weight and volume of the silver cells be utilized in a sufficiently reversible way. Andre's previous experience in colloids in the mid 1920's made him believe that part of the trouble with the zinc and silver electrodes could be resolved by a regenerated cellulosic membrane. At first he made his own (2) by treating nitrocellulose and aceto-cellulose in order to obtain a semipermeable membrane; the

first membrane patent was issued in 1932. An early U.S. patent by Andre (3) specified a storage battery with semipermeable separation based on regenerated cellulose (cellophane) and special electrode arrangements.

As stated by A. Fleischer (4), "...the requirements for preventing the diffusion of silver oxide [to the negative] and the growth of zinc in trails [towards the positive] are marginally met by the use of regenerated cellulosic film, usually cellophane or regenerated sausage casing in combination with porous electrolyte absorbent separators. Generally, the cellulose film has been applied in multiple layers in the composite separator system."

The nature of cellulosic films is affected by the source of the raw material stock, e.g. wood pulp vs. cotton linters, and the film forming process chemistry and mechanics. Wood is on average, 40-50% cellulose, the remainder being lignin and other non-cellulosic entities. Cotton is predominantly

cellulose and may contain as little as 3% impurities (5). Cellulose is polydisperse and the average polymer chain length depends on the source and the method of purification. In native cotton cellulose, the average chain length can be more than 3500, whereas it is commonly 700-1300 in wood pulps. In commercial regenerated cellulose from wood (by the viscose process), typical average chain length is 200-600. In the fabrication of films, a stretching step is included which increases the tensile properties in the direction of the stretch, usually the machine direction, although it is possible to stretch film in the transverse direction as well, to improve transverse properties.

Introduction

The separator currently used in silver-zinc rechargeable cells for a great many Navy applications is a cellophane film derived from wood pulp by a standard viscose process. The film is typically drawn to a thickness of 1 mil, and usually five or six layers are used to wrap the cathode (silver plate) in the cells, to minimize silver migration and retard zinc dendrite growth. The film is slowly hydrolyzed in the strongly alkaline conditions of the cell chemistry, so it is also a sacrificial membrane. Thus, the maintenance of barrier properties and physical integrity are important to cycle and wet life of the cells.

Despite the history of testing and evaluation of cellophane films with the intent of improving alkaline rechargeable cell performance, over the past fifteen years a decrease in cell life has occurred in cells built for Navy use. In historical efforts to understand how the physical and chemical properties of various cellulosic materials contribute to the manner in which these materials behave in real silver-zinc rechargeable cells (6-9) there has been an absence of coordination between measurement of separator properties and correlation of that data with cycle and wet-stand life data from a matrix of rechargeable cell tests, followed by thorough failure analysis. Thus, a program was initiated at the NAVSURFWARCENDIV Crane and Rutgers University, with financial support from a number of government entities, to study a set of properties for a variety of source-material and processing-method cellophanes, and then to build a matrix of test cells which incorporated those cellophanes for evaluation by cycle and wet-stand life testing.

A series of physical measurements were performed on separator films including silver and zinc migration rates. Subsequent to the determination of physical properties, a selection from the separator films currently available from various manufacturers was built into model cells for cycle and wet life testing. The separators were selected to represent a cross section of their property characteristics so that a

correlation could be obtained between these properties and cell performance. The test cells were built from a single stock of silver and zinc plates of identical thickness and loading, containing NAVSEC-1 composition (10) in place of mercury in the anodes, and filled with identical composition electrolyte. The combined wet thickness of the separator for the cathode wrap was also constant. Therefore, the only variable from one cell set to another was the separator film used. A sufficient number of cells with each separator type was utilized in assembling a test matrix to provide statistical reliability for the data collected for cycle and wet life, and all cells were to be treated identically in the test program. Finally, analysis was performed on the separators at intervals during the testing and at the conclusion of cell life to determine the mechanisms for material and cell mechanical failure which resulted from the cell cycling procedures.

The final intention from this testing is to transition the results to industry by writing a separator specification based on the separator physical property and cell test data which will emphasize the use of cellophanes with optimal properties of resistance to silver ion migration and oxidation, resistance to zinc dendrite growth, and resistance to degradation effects of the alkaline environment. By defining the characteristics of cellophane which are responsible for the optimization of these properties, the specification will require manufacturers of cellophane separator to produce films with the desirable physical properties. By also writing the specification into contracts for cell manufacture, cells of optimum performance will be produced. The specification will also allow quality control of materials for consistent battery performance.

Testing

A total of one hundred four (104) 30 Ah (nominal) low-rate cells, with unformed plates (i.e., uncharged), but filled with electrolyte at the manufacture, were divided into eight sets, based on the eight types of separator used to build the cells, as follows:

- Set 1 - 6 layers standard 1 mil wood pulp (WP) cellophane
- Set 2 - 6 layers 1 mil WP silver-treated cellophane
- Set 3 - 6 layers 1 mil cotton cellophane
- Set 4 - 6 layers 1 mil WP cellophane (alternative manufacture from Set 1)
- Set 5 - 1 layer 1 mil WP cellophane + 3 layers 1.75 mil WP sausage casing (SC)
- Set 6 - 2 layers 3 mil fiber-reinforced WP-SC
- Set 7 - 6 layers 1 mil PVA-coated WP cellophane
- Set 8 - 1 layer of 1 mil WP cellophane + 2 layers 3 mil polyamide fiber-reinforced viscose SC

These eight sets were further divided into three Groups per set. Group 1 from each set consisted of one cell which was

formed by charge-discharge cycling and then dissected and analyzed for baseline separator proper- properties. Group 2 from each set consisted of five cells which were formed and placed on wet-stand test. Group 3 consisted of seven cells which were formed and placed on cycle life test.

Group 1, Baseline

One cell from each set served as a baseline cell. It was weighed, measured, and "formed" by charge-discharge cycling, at a C/30 (1 A) rate to 2.03 V followed by a C/60 (0.5 A) rate to 2.03 V for charge, and C/15 (2 A) rate to 1.30 V for discharge, with an equilibration time of 2 hours between each charge and discharge cycle. The final discharge was at a C/5 (6 A) rate to 1.30 V before dissection. These cells were reweighed, remeasured, and dissected.

Group 2, Wet Life Testing

Five cells from each set were weighed, measured, and formed as above. At the completion of the formation cycling, a C/5 discharge was performed, the cells were recharged at a C/15 rate, and placed on 30-day wet stand at ambient temperature. After 29-31 days (depending on weekends and holidays), these cells were discharged at a C/5 rate to 1.30 V, allowed to equilibrate for 2 hours, recharged at a C/15 rate to 2.03 V, and replaced on wet-stand. This cycle will continue for each cell in all sets until the discharge capacity for each cell on a given cycle drops below 50% of initial capacity, at which time that cell is withdrawn from test, discharged, and subjected to failure analysis. One cell from each set is also withdrawn from test for analysis at 6 and 12 months. Logs of initial capacity and charge/ discharge performance are maintained for each cell.

Group 3, Cycle Life Testing

Seven cells from each set were weighed, measured, and formed as before. The charge and discharge cycling procedure are continued for each cell in all sets at a C/15 rate to 2.03 V and a C/5 rate to 1.30 V until the discharge capacity for each cell on a given cycle drops below 50% of initial capacity, at which time that cell is withdrawn from test, discharged, and subjected to failure analysis. One cell from each set is also withdrawn for analysis at 50 and 100 cycles. Logs of initial capacity and charge/discharge performance are maintained for each cell.

A second failure method was defined for all cycle and wet life charging, such that if a cell failed to accept at least 90% of the previous discharge capacity, the cell charge/discharge data would be examined to determine whether the cell should be withdrawn from test and subjected to failure analysis.

Separator Tests

Physical testing to characterize the changes in separator properties as a function of cell life include silver penetration per separator layer to provide data on the extent of silver migration in each of the separator materials, and zinc penetration to determine the resistance of the various separators to zinc dendrite formation.

Results and Analysis

Silver Migration Data

In Table 1 are presented the data for the silver concentration as mg/cm² of separator layer for each of the layers in each cell from the life cycle sets. These data are for baseline (B), failed (F), and 50-cycle cells. The first layer on all cathodes is a 2 mil layer of Webril, a 2 mil (wet thickness) non-woven polypropylene. This material does a relatively poor job of stopping silver migration but aids in wetting the plate. In comparing the data for the baseline cells from Sets 1, 2, 3, 4, and 7, all of which had six layers of 1 mil cellophane film wrap, it is first interesting to note that in those cases where the silver concentration in the fiber layer was comparatively high (Sets 3 and 4), the concentration in layer 1 was also high, while layers 2, 3, and 4 were comparatively smaller, indicating that in Sets 3 and 4 the silver migration was stopped by the first cellophane layer during the 7 cycles of formation cycling. It also appears that the 1 mil cellophane from cotton did the best job of stopping silver migration overall, at this early stage. At 50 cycles, from the data available (Set 3 cycling was discontinued early in cycling because the capacity performance was terrible, *(vide infra)*), it appears that there is still little silver migration beyond layer 4 for the 1 mil cellophane film sets, even though significant quantities of silver appear to have accumulated in some of the separator samples (Table 2). These data for 1 mil cellophane sets indicate that the films in Sets 1 and 4 are allowing greater amounts of silver to migrate, but that the outer film layers are doing a better job of stopping the migration, while the films in Sets 2 and 7 are keeping the total migration to a minimum.

In order to compare the performance of the SC separators, the data were normalized to a constant wet thickness, based on the data for this property in Table 3, which gives the data in Table 4, where 3 mil was selected as the standard. Before proceeding further, it is necessary to note that Sets 5 and 8 in Table 4 had one layer of 1 mil cellophane film wrap as the first layer. Secondly, there are repetitive values for silver concentration in successive layers for these three sets because one layer of SC was equivalent to 2+ layers of 1 mil cellophane (cf. Table 2). Strict comparisons between SC and 1 mil films are also difficult because there is no way of

Table 1. Total Silver Concentration (mg/cm²) per Separator Layer

Sample	Fiber Layer	Layer 1	Layer 2	Layer 3	Layer 4	Layer 5	Layer 6
S1-13-B	0.1372	0.8087	0.1278	0.0150	6 E-4	0	2.4 E-3
S1-6-50	0.2118	4.513	1.579	0.3246	1 E-4	1 E-4	0
S2-2-B	0.0857	1.066	0.3780	0.0594	0.0107	4.88 E-3	6.10 E-3
S2-7-50	0.0323	0.9320	0.9025	0.7615	0.0166	6.0 E-3	4.1 E-3
S3-11-B	1.113	2.418	0.0404	1.28 E-3	1.19 E-3	7.85 E-4	2.12E-3
S4-13-B	0.2185	1.675	0.0896	2.1 E-3	1.0 E-3	2 E-4	2 E-4
S4-6-50	0.1539	2.778	1.231	0.3618	0.0428	2 E-4	1 E-4
S5-13-B	0.1046	0.4394	0.1213	0.0165	0.0175	-	-
S6-13-B	0.1415	1.242	6.2 E-3	-	-	-	-
S7-1-B	0.1422	0.5514	0.1858	0.120	4.74 E-3	8 E-5	5 E-5
S7-10-50	0.2063	1.382	1.145	0.3935	0.0304	9 E-4	7 E-4
S8-13-B	0.1164	2.8532	0.1475	4.27 E-3	-	-	-

Table 2. Accumulated Silver (mg/cm²) Through Layer 4

Separator Sample	Baseline	50 Cycle
S1 - 1 mil untreated	1.095	4.454
S2 - 1 mil Ag treated	1.599	2.645
S4 - 1 mil untreated	1.986	4.568
S7 - 1 mil PVA treated	1.004	3.157

Table 3. Thickness (in mils) in 45% KOH

Separator	Thickness - Dry	Thickness - Soaked
Set 1, WP film, 1 mil	1.19±0.04	3.01±0.03
Set 2, WP film, 1 mil Ag trt'd	1.13±0.04	3.01±0.03
Set 3, Cotton film, 1 mil	1.07±0.02	2.28±0.10
Set 4, WP film, 1 mil	1.14±0.07	2.94±0.12
Set 5, WP SC, 1.75 mil	2.29±0.00	7.24±0.02
Set 6, WP SC, 6 mil fibre-reinf.	5.91±0.71	7.81±0.09
Set 7, WP film, PVA ctd., 1 mil	1.19±0.04	3.01±0.03
Set 8, WP SC, 3 mil PA reinf.	4.59±0.19	7.00±0.38

Table 4. Normalized Silver Concentration (mg/cm²/3 mil) per Separator Layer

Sample	Fiber Layer*	Layer 1	Layer 2	Layer 3	Layer 4	Layer 5	Layer 6
S1-13-B	0.1372	0.8087	0.1278	0.0150	6 E-4	0	2.4 E-3
S1-6-50	0.2118	4.513	1.579	0.3246	1 E-4	1 E-4	0
S2-2-B	0.0857	1.066	0.3780	0.0594	0.0107	4.88 E-3	6.10 E-3
S2-7-50	0.0323	0.9320	0.9025	0.7615	0.0166	6.00 E-3	4.10 E-3
S3-11-B	1.113	3.182	0.0532	1.68 E-3	1.57 E-3	1.03 E-3	2.79 E-3
S4-13-B	0.2185	1.6750	0.0896	2.11 E-3	1.05 E-3	2.2 E-4	2.0 E-4
S4-5-50	0.1539	2.778	1.231	0.3618	0.0428	2 E-4	1 E-4
S5-13-B	0.1046	0.4394	0.0503	0.0503	0.0286	6.84 E-3	6.84 E-3
S6-13-B	0.1415						
S7-1-B	0.1422	0.5514	0.1858	0.1202	4.74 E-3	8 E-5	5 E-5
S7-10-50	0.2063	1.382	1.145	0.3935	0.0304	9.0 E-4	7.0 E-4
S8-13-B	0.1164	2.853	0.0632	0.0632	0.0223	1.83 E-3	1.83 E-3

knowing whether the silver in a layer of SC is evenly distributed throughout the layer (as has been assumed in performing the normalizations and distribution), or whether the SC in each case has served as an effective barrier so that the silver is concentrated at the surface closest to the cathode. In comparing just the three SC sets, it appears that the fiber-reinforced SC (Set 6) was a better barrier to silver migration than the 1.75 mil SC (Set 5), even though they are of comparable wet thickness (Table 3). It also may be that the polyamide fiber SC was the best of the three, because both it and Set 5 had a layer of 1 mil cellophane as the first layer, and the backup of silver on this layer was much greater for Set 8 than for Set 5. Comparison of these data with 1 mil film in the absence of 50 cycle cell data are too tenuous for any conclusions to be drawn.

Zinc Migration Data

The zinc migration data are presented in Table 5. The data are arranged as proceeding from anode (Layer 6) to cathode (Webril Layer). Again, it is most informative to compare the 1 mil film Sets 1, 2, 3, 4, and 7 first. In the baseline cell data for these five separators, all but Set 1 data are about the same in respective layers, 0.10-0.15 mg/cm² zinc per layer, and the values for a specific separator appear to be consistent from layer to layer. The values for the layer closest to the anode, Layer 6, are not reliable because zinc from the anode tended to adhere to this film layer. Set 4 appeared to have the lowest zinc content per layer. Then, in comparing the 50-cycle cell data to the respective baseline data, in every cell set except Set 1, there was an increase in zinc content per layer, and again the values from layer to layer within a set, including Set 1, are fairly constant, with only a slight increase in zinc content from left (anode) to right (cathode). Thus it would appear that the principal mechanism for zinc is deposition from solution into the separator film layers during charge/discharge processes, rather than migration from the anode toward the cathode during cycling.

As for the SC Sets 5, 6, and 8, if the data are normalized for separator thickness to 3 mil, Set 5 (Layers 3 and 2, (Layer 1 is 1 mil cellophane)) and Set 6 (Layer 1) are not far off the baseline data for the 1 mil films (0.28-0.27 for Set 5, and 0.26 for Set 6), where the outermost layer adjacent to the anode is neglected because of the contact with that plate. Of interest, though, are the data for Set 8, which are quite high in zinc, because these cells failed early in their cycle life due to zinc dendrite formation, which is reflected in the high zinc content in the separator layers.

Cell Testing

When the cell cycle life testing was begun, it soon became

apparent that the test regime of C/15 charge and C/5 discharge was giving very poor capacity performance, in comparison to that obtained during the cell formation cycling (cf., e.g., Figure 1). Therefore, after several cycles, the regime was changed to a C/30 charge to 1.95 V, then a C/60 charge to 2.03 V, followed by the C/5 discharge. Immediately, the cells returned to the charge capacity behavior observed during the formation process, so that this regime is maintained for the remainder of the cycling for both life and wet stand cycling. The cells on cycle life are at or beyond 50 cycles. Problems arose with several of these cell sets, which will be explained subsequently.

Sets 1 and 2 differ only in the fact that the separator, which comes from the same manufacturer, was untreated in Set 1, and coated with metallic silver in Set 2. The charge and discharge capacity data for the two sets compare well, although in the latter set, charge acceptance and discharge capacity in the 40-50 cycle region appear somewhat better. Set 1 contains six cells at 64 cycles and Set 2 contains four at 55 cycles. An interesting observation regarding the separators from these two sets at 50 cycles was that the untreated film was much less robust during dissection. A typical plot of capacity vs. cycles is presented in Figure 1 for Set 1, which has the greatest accumulated cycle life at this time.

For Set 4 only three of the original seven cells are still cycling, and the capacity data show a substantial drop-off in charge and discharge capacities in the 40-50 cycle region, compared to Sets 1 and 2. Cells from Set 4 have failed due to hot shorts at cycles 4 and 6 (during formation), and at cycle 14, and a fourth cell failed at cycle 12 due to low discharge capacity. Only preliminary analysis has been performed on these cells to date, and the cells have been frozen to preserve them until more detailed analyses can be performed.

Of the original seven cells in Set 5, which contains 1.75 mil SC, only three are still on test (two were lost at cycle 36, and another at cycle 40), and a significant divergence appeared at cycle 30 between charge and discharge capacities. These cells are only at 42 cycles. One cell was removed at cycle 24 because the cell cases were bulging, and it was discovered that because of a miscalculation when the cell design was established, three layers of SC were used instead of two, as required by wet thickness. Consequently, the internal stack pressure is about 20% greater than for Sets 1 and 2, and this is expected to be reflected in poor cycle and wet life performance.

The cells in Set 7 are exhibiting internally consistent behavior, although four of the seven cells have been lost to hot shorts. The individual cell capacities are quite close

Table 5. Total Zinc Concentration (mg/cm²) per Separator Layer

Sample	Layer 6	Layer 5	Layer 4	Layer 3	Layer 2	Layer 1	Webril
S1-13-B	0.3555	0.1768	0.4429	0.5673	0.2908	0.4353	00391
S1-6-50	0.4764	0.4154	0.3798	0.4162	0.4230	0.5007	0.0876
S2-2-B	0.1628	0.1546	0.1612	0.1656	0.1575	0.1541	0.0045
S2-7-50	0.3035	0.3024	0.2902	0.3299	0.3611	0.3698	0.1515
S3-11-B	0.1390	0.1025	0.1050	0.1040	0.1156	0.1393	0.0268
S4-13-B	0.1498	0.1451	0.0875	0.0928	0.0860	0.0972	0.0130
S4-5-50	0.3683	0.2986	0.2929	0.3047	0.3272	0.3815	0.0495
S5-13-B	-	-	0.7011	0.6721	0.6447	0.4412	0.0699
S6-13-B	-	-	-	-	1.935	0.6760	0.0711
S7-1-B	0.1629	0.1268	0.1216	0.1122	0.1057	0.1016	0.0075
S7-10-50	0.3208	0.2024	0.3710	0.2959	0.3152	0.3231	0.0778
S8-13-B	-	-	-	2.497	2.541	0.6422	0.0282

together and the cells appear to be holding up about as well between 40 and 50 cycles as Sets 1 and 2. This separator film has the same manufacturer as that in Sets 1 and 2, but the film was coated with polyvinyl alcohol from solution, in an attempt to reduce silver penetration.

Four sets of cells failed early in this study, for the following reasons:

Set 3 - this cell set was built with an internal plastic shim to provide matching internal stack pressure to Sets 1, 2, and 4. This shim has been found to dissolve in 45% KOH, leading to excessively large internal impedance, and the cells accept charge very poorly.

Set 5 - as already mentioned, this cell set is expected to exhibit poor performance because the internal stack pressure is about 20% too great, because one too many layers of separator were used.

Set 6 - the separator cracked and split at the U-wrap corners because the folds at these points were stressed by the cell case constraints, leading to zinc intrusion to the cathodes and hot shorts.

Set 8 - the original separator was polyamide fiber coated on one side with viscose, and the cathode wrap was such that the uncoated side faced the anodes, allowing swift zinc dendrite penetration.

These four sets have been rebuilt with the following changes in the cell designs:

Set 3 - a cell case which will accommodate the less swollen separator without the need for shims.

Set 5 - 1 layer of 1 mil SC + 2 layers of 1.75 mil SC instead of three.

Set 6 - a cell case slightly wider than for Sets 1 and 2, to allow for the greater rigidity of 3 mil fiber-reinforced SC.

Set 8 - polyamide fiber-reinforced SC coated on both sides with viscose, to improve barrier properties to zinc dendrites.

Summary

These cell cycle life studies are ongoing, and the wet life cells have only six months of accumulated data, too little to draw any conclusions. Nevertheless, it is already apparent that the separator in Set 4 is failing prematurely, compared to Sets 1 and 2. This may be a reflection of poor separator physical properties. Also, the behavior of cell Set 7 is remarkable, in spite of the loss of four cells to hot shorts, for the closeness of charge and discharge capacities, and also for the fact that these cells are showing a very narrow distribution of capacities over the cell set, 2 Ah, compared to both Sets 1 and 2 which are exhibiting distributions of 3-4 Ah (Set 1), and 6 Ah (Set 2). Finally, Sets 1 and 2 are very close in

average Ah performance through cycle 50, so that expected differences due to silver coating of the separator film is not yet showing up in cell performance.

It is expected that this study will provide a "best set" of separator physical properties for future silver-zinc cell design, and it will be very informative, then, to extend this work to other rechargeable alkaline cell chemistries.

Acknowledgements

This work was generously supported by the Standard Hardware Acquisition and Reliability Program at the Naval Surface Warfare Center, Crane IN, the Office of Naval Research, Washington D.C., the Naval Undersea Warfare Center, Keyport WA, SPECWARCOM, Coronado CA, and NASA-Lewis, Cleveland OH. Thanks are due to Mr. A. Himy, Westinghouse MTD (NAVSEA 03E21) and to Dr. A. Salkind at Rutgers University for technical discussions. Thanks are also in order for Mr. B. Winter at NSWC Crane for providing the plasma spectroscopy data on silver and zinc.

References

1. H. Andre, *Bull. Soc. Franc. Electriciens*, **1**, (1941), p 132.
2. Interview with H. Andre by A.J. Salkind, quoted in "Alkaline Storage Batteries", by S.U. Falk and A.J. Salkind, John Wiley, New York (1969).
3. H. Andre, US Patent 2,317,711 (1943).
4. A. Fleischer in "Characteristics of Separators for Alkaline Silver Oxide Zinc Secondary Batteries", Ed. by J.E. Cooper and A. Fleischer, AF Aero Propulsion Laboratory, **300-sep-65-773-10-216** (1965).
5. "Cellulose", in *The Encyclopedia of Chemistry*, 3rd edition, Ed. by C. Hampel and G. Hawley, D. VanNostrand-Reinhold, New York (1973), pp 217-219.
6. S.U. Falk and A.J. Salkind, "Alkaline Storage Batteries", *op. cit.*, pp 240-276.
7. H.P. Gregor in "Zinc-Silver Oxide Batteries", Ed. by A. Fleischer and J.J. Lander, The Electrochemical Society, Inc., John Wiley & Sons, New York (1971), pp 219-232.
8. A. Himy, "Silver-Zinc Battery - Phenomena and Design Principles", Vantage Press, New York (1995).
9. J.E. Cooper and A. Fleischer, eds., "Characteristics of Separators for Alkaline Silver Oxide Zinc Secondary Batteries" *op. cit.*
10. A. Himy and O.C. Wagner, "Substitutes for Mercury in Alkaline Zinc Batteries (II)," 29th Power Sources Conference Proceedings, Ft. Monmouth, NJ (1978), pp 167-69.
12. R. E. Post, "Zinc-Silver Oxide Batteries", *op. cit.*, p. 263.

Cycle Life - Set 1

Figure 1. Set 1 Separator Average Cell Capacities on Charge and Discharge vs. Cycle Number